

ISic0535

I.Sicily inscription 0535

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2002.06

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Eryx

Place of origin (modern)

Erice

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Erice, Biblioteca comunale, inventory 139

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491758

EDCS 22000841

Bibliography

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